

ROLE OF LIBRARY FOR STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Received, 19 February 2023

Accepted, 1 April 2024

Available Online, 25 April 2024

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ABSTRACT

Libraries have always been essential parts of higher education, acting as centers of research, knowledge repositories, and intellectual crucibles. This study explores the varied functions that libraries perform in the lives of college students. It explores the many roles that libraries play, including the provision of resources, academic support, and the promotion of a positive learning environment. Through knowledgeable librarians, libraries help students navigate these resources, develop their information literacy skills, and improve their research techniques. Libraries offer guidance and support through expert librarians who assist students in navigating these resources, enhancing their information literacy skills, and honing their research abilities. The general objective of this study to investigate the role of the library for students in higher education and how they incorporate them into their learning resources is one of the specific aims of the study. The main library of Zamzam University is the study area where this study was conducted. To experience how learners benefit from the material learning present in the library, written questions were demonstrated among the university faculties. Students from six different departments of three faculties were questioned, 44 percent of them read for one hour at the library. Similarly, 39% of them visit the library twice a week. The majority of students read books related to their chosen course.

Keywords: Higher education, libraries, academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

In higher education, libraries play a crucial role in academic success. Libraries within higher education institutes can nurture and contribute well-educated societies, as well as enabling individuals to empower them (Meyer, 2016). In the 21st century, technological innovation dominates in any sector of life including smart libraries where information is being created and stored. During in our higher learning journey, the library supports us in retrieving the right information, therefore, the library is inevitable for this journey to achieve academic success in higher education (Mondal, 2021). A library is essential to the growth of any community. Libraries produce environmental knowledge and influence the local community. A habit of reading, writing, and analyzing is formed at a library. It implies that the library is essential to a person's development. Since a library is seen as a crucial component of a university education, its position in higher education is far more significant than it is in primary and secondary school. The library network is necessary for academic and research endeavors. The library is a crucial component for any educational program to be successful (Chaudhari, 2018). The Kothari Education Commission (1964-65) underlined that it is more harmful to overlook libraries and give them poor priority. The key element that fosters teaching-learning and research activity is the academic library. It plays a crucial role in achieving the goals and objectives of higher education.

Library works as a platform that provides students in higher education access to resources and services when doing research and other related activities (Rasul & Singh, 2010). Academic libraries acts as research and learning centers of the university, since they allow students to acquire suitable environment of learning enormous information (Foo, Chaudhry, & Majid, 2002). In terms of library services, graduate students at the Science Library were more likely than those at the Law Library to receive the necessary research materials and dependable photocopying services. Additionally, science students were more likely than arts students to significantly rely on interlibrary loans in order to obtain research resources that were not available at the library (Wafaa Al Motawah, Sen, & Willett, 2018).

According to the (Khan, Bhatti, Khan, & Ismail, 2014) university library has an important role in nurturing higher education and implementing the requirements of the university. Students who are doing their higher education should be given to any skills and material they need to master their

chosen subjects. At this point, the university library is among the materials students are to be given. In postgraduate studies, access to library resources and services is crucial for doing fruitful research, showcasing academic scholarship, and winning praise for original thought. The significance of libraries for higher education is undeniable by supporting their academic success (Ajiboye, Bokoh, Bello, & Idowu, 2023). The primary objective of academic libraries and library professionals should be to establish a globally interconnected library system and transform it into a comprehensive knowledge resource center (Rajarm).

In the digital world, academic libraries provide the academicians and students mindset of employing this innovative technology for the preservation and digitalizing the information. Therefore, academic library becomes a backbone of the university services (Sandhu, 2018).

Objectives

- To ascertain the main role of library plays in higher education.
- To find out the time spent in the library by the students.
- To assess ways students pay visit to the library.

RESEARCH DESIGN

To investigate the role of the library in higher education, a quantitative research design was employed on undergraduate students from three faculties of Zamzam University. The data collection tool of the research was an administrated questionnaire. These questions were distributed among the students from the three faculties of Zamzam University, the faculty of Agriculture, the faculty of Medicine and Surgery, and the faculty of Health Science. Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and excel were used for quantitative data analysis.

RESULTS

The respondents are all from six departments of three faculties of agriculture, medicine, and health Science which comprises six departments, 26% agriculture, 44% medicine, 12% lab, 7% nursing and midwifery, 9% public health, and 2 % animal husbandry.

Table 1 and figure 1 indicate that 253 of the respondents 53% of them were female and 47% were male.

All respondents were in the four academic years of the university: first year 9%, second year 15%, third year 44% and fourth year 32% respectively.

Figure 2 reported the days students visit the library. 39% of the respondents showed that they go to the library to read two days in the week, while 36% visit the library to read one day in a week.

Figure 3 below discovers number of hours students spend their time in the library. 44% of the respondents answered 30-60 minutes read in the library and 33% of them read less than 30 minutes, whereas 23% of the respondents answered that more than one hour they read in the library.

The figure 4 below highlights the most favorite books that students prefer to read and their answers indicate how library may shape learning university students. 65% read books about their faculty, while 18% read general books. This proves that students are more interested in reading about related books of their faculty. All students from different faculties of the university have relative capacity of reading as the study presents.

The figure 5 indicates number of books students read in a month. 46% of the research participants answered one book in a month, 42% of the respondents read two books per month and likewise 12% of the respondents don't read one book in a month.

As the figure 6 shows, students select books they read their own criteria. 47% of the respondents read relevant book of their faculties, while 44% of the respondents pick books up for general knowledge, 7% of them select to find out their assignment answers, and lastly 2% of the respondents choose books to read for other purpose.

Figure 7 presents when students pay visit to the library for reading. 57% of them visit the library any time they get chance. 36% of the respondents indicated that break time they go to the library. 2% and 5% of the respondents visit the library when lecture becomes bored and else time respectively.

The figure 8 below reports that reading material was tested. 57% of the students make notes during their reading and 17% use white paper for collecting information. 14% of the respondents take screenshots for collecting information, while 12% of the respondents answered they don't anything for gathering information.

Figure 9 indicates students' motivation of going to library. As the figure shows, 38% of the respondents told their stimuli of compelling visiting the library their reading interest, 27% of them responded they visit the library motivation given by the lecturer, 12% of the respondents answered that their friend's courage to visit and lastly, 23% of them have external factors to motivate to the library.

In this survey, participants were asked that they borrow books from the library as to read beyond the library. Their answer was passionately positive. 56% of the participants borrow books from the library and students make aware their friends to go with library.

DISCUSSION

Libraries are still committed to giving students the tools they need to succeed academically. They are dynamic participants in the search for knowledge and serve as models of learning and creativity in higher education. They are not just informational repositories. Libraries' crucial contribution to producing graduates who are well-rounded, knowledgeable, and engaged highlights their pervasive significance in the contemporary educational scene. This study investigates how students involve reading in the library of the university and as it helps them. Likewise, to measure the level of reading, participating and making use of the library was testing. The respondents showed that the library has an immense role for their learning. As well as the study indicates that students of the university are ready to make use of the library during their learning times. The tested respondents answered that library made positive impact in their learning. Measuring number

of days they visit the library, the result shows reliable information of how library takes part student's learning.

In addition, majority of the students suggested to enhance available services in the library. They suggested to increase books different faculties of the university available in the library. Most of the respondents said that they need book written in Somali language. As well as they requested to hold training sessions of research writing, citation and service facilitates using library such as bringing previous dissertations and guidelines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author surely wants to thank those respondents of the survey for their perception and feedback. Thanks also go to the Zamzam University for allowing to conduct such study in the university library. I hope this study will ignite student's performance and help libraries of the universities and their staff for advancing facilities of the library.

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